

Modeling the Assessment of Household Income and FDI Influence on Nigerian Economic Growth using Vector Autoregressive Approach

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The Nigerian economy has supported sustainable economic development with a variation of GDP for the past decades and at present. Specifically, the main objective of this study is to investigate the current relationship between the determinants of economic development and GDP in Nigeria for the period 1981 to 2017. This study used household final expenditure, FDI, government spending, export, and import to predict the variation of GDP. Initially, we performed the three root unit tests for each selected variable to validate whether the series is stationary or not before determining an optimal lag order and cointegration equation between the series. To assess the relationship within the variables, we applied Johansen cointegration tests. We further employed the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to evaluate the optimum lag order. The error correction term (ECT) was calculated to measure the GDP's adjustment speed to its equilibrium point. Also, Granger causality effects were assessed and the variance decomposition of the forecast error was also predicted. The results from ADF, PP, and KPSS test gave a strong conclusion that the series is stationary at the first difference. An adjustment coefficient value (-0.0858) implies an 8.58 percent-speed correction of the preceding year's deviation from the long run. The ECT's significant p-values (0.0187) showed a long-run relationship between the selected independent variables and GDP. Thus, the estimated error variance of 67.13 percent of GDP would be triggered in the long term by FDI net inflows. Hence, this implies that FDI has a major effect on the Nigerian economy and GDP variation.

From FDI to household consumption, government spending, import, as well as export, the unidirectional causality effect of Granger was observed. Our study recommends policymakers concentrate on foreign direct investment inflows to ensure sustainable economic development

to enhance the GDP value in Nigeria. Policymakers are strongly encouraged to ensure political and economic stability to attract more foreign investors. Financial resources from FDI inflows can be dispersed impartially in the manufacturing and service sectors and hence the nation's export and import will effectively increase household and government spending.

Keywords: Household Income, Government spending, FDI, Economic growth, ECT, Nigeria.

Introduction

Economic Development background of Nigeria

The Nigerian economy experienced steady economic development over the past decades, with annual GDP growth. For example, non-oil activities led to this growth in 2014, and the service sector contributed significantly (57 percent) to the country's GDP. The country's economy thus achieved a degree of diversity which should continue to stimulate growth (Chima, 2017). The Nigerian economy has in many instances been unfree since it emerged from the repressed group in 2007 (Godslove & Okonkwo, 2015). GDP growth over the last five years has been unimpressive for such a resource-rich developing country. This segment examines the composition of the GDP and economic development patterns in Nigeria from 1981 to 2017. The added values of Nigeria's GDP including manufacturing, utilities, and agricultural sectors are expressed in current US dollars. Nigeria's economy suffered a recession during the period chosen between 1981 and 1995. The country has experienced significant GDP growth since 2000 caused by the sectors of those three contributors. **Figure 1** shows that the country's GDP rose steadily from \$44,062 million to \$99,712 million between 1995 and 2015. (World Development Indicators, 2019). The main contributor to GDP is the manufacturing then agricultural and service sectors. The share of the country's industrial sector in the overall GDP has increased significantly from 37.91 percent to 58.09 percent while the share of the agricultural and service sectors has decreased from 36.58 percent to 20.7 percent and 25.51 percent to 21.20 percent over the past decade respectively. The service sector contributes to increasing the total GDP and becomes crucial in the dynamics of Nigerian economic development to a greater extent.

Economic Trend 1981-2017

Figure 1: Nigerian economic development trends and GDP components for the period 1981-2017

Source: Author

Statement of Problem

Through the years, the volatility of growth in the economy’s statistical analysis is the primary purpose of selecting the Federal Republic of Nigeria as an area of study. Although economic indicators including household spending, foreign direct investment, government final expenditure, export, and import have been widely studied individually for economic growth, except that their combination remains uncommon in a single study. The individual effect of each variable on GDP remains an unresolved issue throughout the literature. Capitalizing on these gaps makes a meritorious undertaking of the current research study. There has been empirical evidence, however, which leads to much to be desired on other economic growth determinants. The oil and gas sector’s contributions to Nigerian economic development are mostly the subject of studies although neglecting other causal factors of stated economic growth. General research from the study aimed to analyze and examine other determinants of economic growth; household income, FDI, government spending, export, and impingement on GDP.

Research Objectives

To assess the correlation between GDP and its determinants, this research will discuss the following specific objectives:

- Empirically examine the short-term and long-term relationships between economic variables (household final expenditure, FDI, final government spending, export, and import) and GDP.
- Assess the effect of causality between those variables and GDP from 1981 to 2017 in Nigeria.
- Forecast these determinants in the next decade contributions to GDP variation

Research Questions

In this work the following questions are addressed:

- To what degree do economic determinants (household final expenditure, FDI, government final expenditure, export, and import) and GDP have any short-term or long-term relationships?
- What are the causality effects between those economic determinants and GDP between 1981 and 2017 in Nigeria?
- How will final household spending, FDI, government final expenditure, export, and import contribute to GDP over the next ten years?

Literature Review

Economic history has provided relevant evidence in the literature that household income, trade-openness, government spending, and FDI are the primary stimulus to economic growth in developing countries. Household spending is the value of the last resident household consumption expenditure to meet their primary needs. Sundry studies have highlighted in a detailed literature review the household income's fundamental role in the economic analysis of demand for the emerging economy (Najdi et al., 2019; Oluwatusin and Sekumade, 2016; Udeaja and Obi, 2015). Paleologou, 2019 recently found that household income inequality is growth-enhancing below the threshold, whereas this inequality had a negative or null effect on economic growth above the threshold. Numerous research conducted has been linked to FDI's impact on GDP in developing countries. FDI inflows have been the driving force of this indicator and the development in previous research (Evans, Frank, and Rebecca, 2017).

There is a growing array of literature identifying the impact of government spending on economic growth in developing countries. According to Al-Fawwaz, 2016, government income represents the pillar of GDP toward the increase of the production of the local economy. Thabane and Lebina, 2016 used the autoregressive approach to investigate both causal and long-term relationships between government income and GDP in Lesotho. A stable long-term nexus was found between government spending and GDP from 1980 to 2012. Along these same lines, Biyase and Zwane, 2015 using the Pooled Ordinary Least Square Strategy to demonstrate that government spending in 30 African countries played a major role in economic development from 1990 to 2005. In the case of Malaysia, the Ordinary Least Squared approach was used to evaluate the impacts of government income on the country's GDP (Hasnul, 2016). These outcomes revealed that for the last 45 years there has been a negative correlation between government spending and economic development in the country. An analysis carried out by Kamasa and Ofori-Abebrese, 2015 using Vector Autoregressive (VAR), stated that the causality effect occurs only in the case of Ghana's economy from GDP to government revenue. Iheanacho, 2016 performed Johansen co-integration and ECT to confirm the collective effect of public expenditure on Nigeria's economic growth during the period 1986-2014.

This segment will examine briefly the correlation between economic growth and open trade. Numerous studies have attempted to provide theoretical proof of the role of trade openness in economic development. Zahonogo, 2017 found that trade openness may have a positive long-term impact on growth, but the effect is not linear on the data from 42 SSA countries covering the period 1980-2012 with the Pooled Mean Group estimation technique. Babalola et al., 2019 identified short and long-run causal associations between international trade and economic development. The study shows that foreign trade has significant long-term consequences for development in Nigeria. Olayungbo, 2019, throughout the study, adopting the Bayesian Time-Varying Parameter model found that oil exports contribute significantly to the Nigerian economy. In Panama, it has been determined that there is no relationship between GDP, exports, and imports despite recent findings of a trade-opening position in economic growth (Bakari and Mabrouki, 2017). Nevertheless, this research found a strong bidirectional causality impact of imports on GDP and exports. More analysis has shown an insignificant short-term relationship between trade openness and imports, while exports and trade balance have significant short-and long-term relationships (Lawal & Ezeuchenne, 2017). The present study differs from prior ones in the scope of the recent year time-series and thereby offering the opportunity to explore the differential impact of household income, FDI, government expenditure, and trade openness in connection with Nigeria's economic growth.

Methodology

Study Area

The Federal Republic of Nigeria is a former British colony and also the most populated country in Sub-Saharan Africa with a current population of 205.2 million, and an immense economy dependent on the oil and gas sector as its major source of government revenue and foreign exchange income (Tomlinson, 2018). Then, after the global economic crisis of 2008/2009 (Arieff et al., 2011), active recapitalization and improved supervision in the banking sector were carried out (Arieff et al., 2010). Nigeria's fiscal development thenceforth propelled by waxing in sectors such as agriculture, telecommunications, and other services. Despite this, both booming evolution and a commercial assortment cannot be translated into any significant drop-off in poverty lines. Narrowly, Nigeria still has over 180 million people living in abject poverty (Senkus et al., 2018). Despite all the meager resources of the world, the affluent in the oil-rich country are submerged under the aegis of low electricity supplies (Ikein, 2016). Regulatory refrain like safety threats narrowed the financing aspect in the oil and gas sector. Since 2012, Nigeria's oil production has continued to dwindle annually until a tiny boomerang in 2017.

Sources of data

The main focus of this research is to empirically assess the relationship between GDP and determinants of economic development using time-series data over the period 1981-2017. The database for our study was

gathered from World Development Indicators (2019). The foregoing listed variables from our analysis included the final household spending, FDI, government expenditure, export, and import used as explanatory variables while the target variable is GDP. Based on the economic theory, the independent variables in this analysis are supposed to connect with Nigeria's gross domestic product. We, therefore, start by identifying the variables selected in **Table 1** before examining the relationship between determinants of economic development and GDP in Nigeria over this study period.

Table 1. Selected Variables Description

Variable	Description	Unit of measure
Dependent variable		
LnGDP	Gross domestic product	(current US\$)
Independent variables		
LnHCONS	Households and NPISHs Final consumption expenditure	(current US\$)
LnFDI	Foreign direct investment, net inflows	(BoP, current US\$)
LnGOVEXP	General government final consumption expenditure	(current US\$)
LnEXPT	Exports of goods and services	(current US\$)
LnIMPT	Imports of goods and services	(current US\$)

Data analysis

This study first performed unit root tests for each selected variable to validate whether the series have unit roots or not before determining the optimal lag order (Ramirez, 2007). Then, to assess the relationship within the variables we applied Johansen cointegration tests (Neal, 2014). Once the long-run relationship has been checked, VECM was performed to estimate the adjustment speed of our dependent variable (GDP) to its level of equilibrium (Hashimzade et al., 2013). The residual diagnostics were done to evaluate the normality, heteroscedasticity, and also the series correlation of our model. To test the stability of the model, inverse roots of the characteristic AR Polynomial were performed. Additionally, to indicate the percentage contribution caused by unexpected variations or shocks of each explanatory variable (HCONS, FDI, GOVEXP, EXPT, and IMPT) on the dependent variable (GDP) in the next ten years, the variance decomposition of the forecast error was utilized. Lastly, for determining causal effects between variables used in our built model, Granger causality tests were performed.

Model Specification

The general model is written as equations below:

$$y_t = (LnGDP_t) = f(HCONS_t, FDI_t, GOVEXP_t, EXPT_t, IMPT_t) \quad (1)$$

The econometric specification is written as follows:

VAR(k) is:

$$(\text{LnGDP}_t) = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_4 \\ \alpha_5 \end{pmatrix} + \sum_{i=1}^k \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_{11} & \varphi_{12} & \varphi_{13} & \varphi_{14} & \varphi_{15} \\ \varphi_{21} & \varphi_{22} & \varphi_{23} & \varphi_{24} & \varphi_{25} \\ \varphi_{31} & \varphi_{32} & \varphi_{33} & \varphi_{34} & \varphi_{35} \\ \varphi_{41} & \varphi_{42} & \varphi_{43} & \varphi_{44} & \varphi_{45} \\ \varphi_{51} & \varphi_{52} & \varphi_{53} & \varphi_{54} & \varphi_{55} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \text{LnHCONS}_{t-1} \\ \text{LnFDI}_{t-1} \\ \text{LnGOVEXP}_{t-1} \\ \text{LnEXPT}_{t-1} \\ \text{LnIMPT}_{t-1} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_3 \\ \varepsilon_4 \\ \varepsilon_4 \\ \varepsilon_5 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where:

t = time dimension,

Ln = natural logarithm,

α_i = matrix of the auto-regressive coefficients

ε_t = matrix of the residuals.

VAR model estimation was applied to test the complex connections between multiple time series variables and also to evaluate the connections between GDP and the determinants affecting economic development in Nigeria, a VAR method was used in this study. Consequently, the general model VAR(k) is considered as:

$$y_t = \alpha_i + \sum_{i=1}^k \varphi_i y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where:

y_t = $n \times 1$ vector of endogenous variables,

φ = $n \times n$ matrix of the auto-regressive coefficients for $i=1 \dots k$,

α = intercept vector,

ε = white noise process.

VAR(k) is written in this analysis, as follows:

The econometric specification states the following:

$$\Delta \text{LnGDP}_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \beta_i \Delta \text{LnGDP}_{t-i} + \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \varphi_m \Delta \text{LnHCONS}_{t-m} + \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} \psi_l \Delta \text{LnFDI}_{t-l} + \sum_{n=1}^{k-1} \delta_n \Delta \text{LnGOVEXP}_{t-n} + \sum_{p=1}^{k-1} \phi_p \Delta \text{LnEXPT}_{t-p} + \sum_{q=1}^{k-1} \omega_q \Delta \text{LnIMPT}_{t-q} + \lambda_1 \text{ECT}_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{1t} \quad (4)$$

Where: $k - 1$ is the optimal lag length reduced by 1. β_i , θ_j , φ_m , ψ_l , δ_n , ϕ_p , and ω_q are the Short-run dynamic coefficients of the model's adjustment of Long-run equilibrium. λ_i is the speed of adjustment parameter with

a negative sign and ECT_{t-1} is the error correction term being the lagged value of the residuals obtained from the cointegration regression of the GDP on the explanatory variables. This ECT contains long-run information derived from the Short-run cointegration relationship. ε_{it} represents the residual of the model.

Results and Discussion

Unit Root Tests

We discuss the following, results of ADF, PP, and KPSS statistic tests (Galbraith and Zinde-Walsh, 1999; University of Bath, 2017). **Table 2** provides results derived from the preliminary analysis. ADF analysis revealed that the entire value of the statistical test is greater than the critical value for all the variables used. This indicates that the null hypothesis stated that the series has a unit root, is rejected for all variables. ADF tests did not find a unit root among variables and therefore, the series is stationary. For the series including LnGDP, LnHCONS, LnFDI, LnGOVEXP, LnEXPT, and LnIMPT, the absolute value of PP statistic test is greater than the critical value. Thus according to PP, the null hypothesis is rejected and these series are stationary. Similarly, the KPSS test indicated that for all selected series LM value is lower than the critical value. However, according to KPSS, the null hypothesis stated that the variables are stationary is not rejected and the series is stationary. The three-unit root methods validated the stationarity of the time-series data used in this study at the first difference. ADF, PP, and KPSS results gave a robust conclusion that at the first difference and 5percent level of significance the series is stationary.

Table 2. Unit Root Tests of the Series used in the Model

Variables	ADF (Prob.*)		PP (Prob.*)		KPSS (LM-Stat.)		I(d) Order of integration
	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)	
	Without Trend	Without Trend					
LnGDP	0.923	0.025	0.995	0.007	0.685	0.387	I(1)
LnHCONS	0.593	0.000	0.926	0.000	0.648	0.144	I(1)
LnFDI	0.462	0.000	0.573	0.000	0.632	0.311	I(1)
LnGOVEXP	0.899	0.000	0.859	0.000	0.506	0.271	I(1)
LnEXPT	0.730	0.000	0.757	0.000	0.619	0.133	I(1)
LnIMPT	0.860	0.000	0.828	0.001	0.621	0.219	I(1)
					Critical value of KPSS		
					1 percent-level	0.739	
					5 percent -level	0.463	
					10 percent-level	0.347	

Optimal Lag (p) Determination and Cointegration Tests

One significant aspect when constructing the VECM model is optimal lag determination. The optimal lag-length represents the complex characteristics of the model effectively. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) is a commonly used tool for evaluating optimum lag order. The optimal lag to the model in this analysis is lag (1) (**Table 3**), according to AIC. The stationarity tests showed that all the series used in our designed models are stationary at difference. Nonetheless, we presumed that these variables (null hypothesis) do not

have a co-integration relation. The Johansen cointegration test is conducted to assess if there is a long-term stable equilibrium relationship between GDP and its determinants in Nigeria. The findings in **Table 4** shows that the Trace statistics value is greater than the critical values and the null hypothesis presuming that there exists no cointegrating equation is rejected. The Johansen statistics revealed that the variables are cointegrated and identified one cointegrating equation. The findings are consistent with a plethora of literature views of FDI, and the household mechanism is significant determinant of economic growth and GDP (Nweze and Edame, 2016; Su and Liu, 2016; Hayat, 2018). Therefore, despite the potential deviation from equilibrium levels in the short-term, there is a linear combination between variables over the whole period. This implies the existence of a long-run causality relationship between GDP and economic growth determinants (HCONS, FDI, GOVEXP, EXPT, and IMPT). Therefore, in this study, the appropriate estimation model to be used is VECM.

Table 3. VAR Lag Length Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-89.60262	NA	9.50E-06	5.463007	5.729638	5.555048
1	61.35566	241.5333*	1.38e-08*	-1.106038*	0.760380*	-0.461751*
2	86.24207	31.28577	3.15E-08	-0.470975	2.995229	0.725558

* indicates Lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5 percent-level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Table 4. Johansen Cointegration Test

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	t-stat.	Trace statistic		Maximum eigenvalue statistic		
		0.05 Critical value	<i>p-value</i>	t-stat.	0.05 Critical value	<i>p-value</i>
None *	96.188	95.754	0.047	38.685	40.078	0.071
At most 1	57.503	69.819	0.320	28.715	33.877	0.182
At most 2	28.787	47.856	0.778	12.824	27.584	0.894
At most 3	15.963	29.797	0.715	11.067	21.132	0.641
At most 4	4.896	15.495	0.820	4.124	14.265	0.846
At most 5	0.772	3.841	0.380	0.772	3.841	0.380

* Denotes rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance

Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

Max-eigenvalue test indicates no cointegration at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) *p-values*

Vector Error Correction Models (VECM) Estimated

The research set out to assess empirically the short-run and long-run relationships between GDP and the economic variables (household final expenditure, FDI, government final expenditure, export, and import). Thus, ECT was estimated to identified the relationship between GDP and these variables (Hashimzade et al.,

2013). The summary of the VECM results is in **Table 5**, and the negative and significance at 1 percent-level of the coefficient of ECT indicated that all the selected variables fit well the model. The ECT measures the adjustment speed of the dependent variable to its level of equilibrium. This coefficient illustrates that any short-term fluctuations between the dependent variable and independent variables will give rise to a stable long-run relationship among the variables in the selected model. The adjustment coefficient value of -0.0858 in this model, indicates that the previous year's deviation from the long-run equilibrium is corrected at 8.58 percent-speed. The significant *p-values* (0.0187) of the VECM indicates that a long-run equilibrium relationship exists between GDP and the selected explanatory variables (HCONS, FDI, GOVEXP, EXPT, and IMPT). The negative sign of the ECT coefficient and significant *p-values* from VECM analysis imply that the model is suitable for forecasting to formulate suitable policy recommendations. A percentage change in HCONS and EXPT in the short run is associated with 2.51 percent and 1.17 percent-decrease of GDP respectively in average *ceteris paribus*. While, a 1 percent-change in FDI, government expenditure, and import is associated with 0.23 percent, 0.80 percent, and 3.13 percent-increase of GDP respectively in average *ceteris paribus*. In Nigeria, FDI, GOVEXP, IMPT led to improve GDP value (current US\$) and the country's economic growth from 1981 to 2017. This is further explained by the fact that in Nigeria, economic dependency requires a shift to include FDI, export and import, household income to sparingly witness massive economic growth from other sectors. The long-run determination is economically good for the Nigerian economy. The findings provided ample evidence supporting that LNHCONS(-1) and LNEXPT (-1) negatively affected the GDP value, and that LNFDI(-1), LNGOVEXP(-1) and LNIMPT(-1) had a positive effect.

Table 5. Statistical Values of the Vector Error Correction Estimated Models

Regressor	Coef.	Std. Error	t-stat	
Long-Run				
LNGDP(-1)	1			
LNHCONS(-1)	-0.9153	-0.0976	-9.3794	
LNFDI(-1)	-0.2063	-0.0655	-3.1519	
LNGOVEXP(-1)	0.3574	-0.0581	6.1497	
LNEXPT(-1)	-0.7388	-0.1570	-4.7050	
LNIMPT(-1)	0.8030	-0.1399	5.7390	
Short-Run				
	Coef.	Std. Error	t-stat	<i>p-value</i>
ECT (CointEq1)	-0.0858	0.0343	-2.5017	0.0187
D(LNGDP1(-1))	0.0468	0.2153	0.2173	0.8296
D(LNHCONS(-1))	-0.0251	0.0301	-0.8321	0.4127
D(LNFDI(-1))	0.0023	0.0127	0.1824	0.8566
D(LNGOVEXP(-1))	0.0080	0.0181	0.4435	0.6609
D(LNEXPT(-1))	-0.0117	0.0241	-0.4854	0.6313
D(LNIMPT(-1))	0.0313	0.0256	1.2226	0.2320
C	0.0371	0.0098	3.7696	0.0008

Statistical values of the estimated model

R-squared	0.5071
Adjusted R-squared	0.3793
F-statistic	3.9680
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0042
Durbin-Watson stat	1.9622

Diagnostic and Stability Tests

The diagnostic post-estimation test is important for checking the model's stability in vector error correction analysis. System stability is important in verifying and validating the robustness of the statistical results for further prediction. In this research, the inverse roots of the characteristic polynomial of AR were performed to evaluate the model's stability. Consequently, the result shows the roots with modulus less than one and are located in the unit circle (**Figure 2**). This result means that the VAR equation satisfies the condition of equilibrium and thus our model is stable. The residual serial diagnostic tests of vector error correction estimates were performed to evaluate the model's serial correlation, normality, and heteroscedasticity. In **Table 6** we summarized the results obtained from Vector Error Correction Estimated residual serial diagnostics. The *p-value* (0.9223) of the lag-related LM test indicated the chosen model does not have a serial correlation. Thus, the model does not suffer from any serial correlation. The normality joint *p-value* (0.0000) shows that normally the entire residual structure of the series is not distributed. The heteroscedasticity test (0.8080) shows that the model is not heteroskedastic and this means that our model is fine.

Figure 2. Stability Plot of GDP

Table 6. Residual Diagnostics

Serial Correlation LM Tests		Normality Tests		Heteroskedasticity Tests
Lag	<i>p-value</i>	Variable	<i>p-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>
		1	0.1595	
		2	0.2762	
		3	0.6169	
1	0.9223	4	0.0000	0.8080
		5	0.6202	
		6	0.0005	
		Joint	0.0000	

Forecast Error Variance Decomposition

One particular purpose of our research is to predict the contributions of selected determinants to GDP variation over the next 10 years. The decomposition of variance correctly assesses the relative importance of the variable to another generated by the shocks (Gonzalo and Ng, 2001; Chan and MacDonald, 2015). The variance decomposition of the forecast error indicates the contribution percentage of each variable caused by unexpected variations or shocks from other variables in our built model. **Table 7**, presents the contribution of the variance decomposition of forecast error of the GDP in Nigeria. In our model, from the first up to the ten periods GDP exhibits a weak endogenous influence on itself. On one hand, 15.59 percent of forecast error variance in GDP will be explained by Nigerian household income in the long run (the next decade). On the other hand, 67.13 percent of forecast error variance in GDP will be caused by the net inflows from foreign direct investment in the coming decade. Meaning that FDI has a strong impact on GDP variation in Nigeria (Sultanuzzaman, Fan, Akash, Wang, and Shakij, 2018; Ayub, Azman-Saini, Laila, Mongid, and Ismail, 2019; Táncošová, 2019).

Table 7. Variance Decomposition of Gross Domestic Product (GDP)

Period	S.E.	LNGDP	LNHCONS	LNFDI	LNGOVEXP	LNEXPT	LNIMPT
1	0.47	3.81	14.72	81.48	0.00	0.00	0.00
2	0.53	5.48	17.26	71.49	4.57	1.17	0.03
3	0.66	7.04	16.67	72.30	3.10	0.81	0.09
4	0.73	8.98	16.85	69.37	3.69	0.68	0.42
5	0.82	10.09	16.23	69.24	3.26	0.58	0.60
6	0.88	11.03	16.08	68.19	3.41	0.50	0.78
7	0.95	11.56	15.84	68.01	3.28	0.44	0.87
8	1.01	12.02	15.76	67.56	3.32	0.39	0.95
9	1.06	12.34	15.65	67.38	3.28	0.35	1.00
10	1.12	12.62	15.59	67.13	3.28	0.32	1.05

Granger Causality Effects

This study conducted the Granger test to assess the causality effects among the variables used in the constructed model. According to the Granger analysis, the null hypothesis is rejected if the *F-statistics'* probability value is less than 5 percent (Ray, 2012). The results in **Table 8** indicate that LNGDP will cause long-run Granger effects in the model on LNFDI, LNGOVEXP, LNEXPT, and LNIMPT. The effect of the Granger causality is unidirectional from GDP to net FDI inflows (Mohanasundaram and Karthikeyan, 2015), Nigeria's final Government expenditure, imports, and exports (Ali Bekhet and Al-Smadi, 2016; Doku, Akuma, and Owusu-Afriyie, 2017). This means that long-term policies and projects should focus on building GDP around the household, exporting e-commerce technology, and importing to attract more foreign investors, stimulating government spending, imports, and exports that will create more employment opportunities and improve well-being for Nigerian households. LNFDI will have a long-run causal effect on LNHCONS, LNGOVEXP, LNEXPT, and LNIMPT by the statistical significance of the *p-values* (0.0240; 0.0128; 0.0278; and 0.0010). There is unidirectional effect of causality in Granger from FDI to household consumption, government spending, imports, and exports. FDI is a key factor in encouraging household consumption and government spending (Gupta and Singh, 2016), and international trade in the Nigerian economy (Seker, Ertugrul, and Cetin, 2015; Pandya, 2016). This study, therefore, recommends FDI servicing on international trade, magnifying the export opportunity and e-commerce import. LNEXPT will also have causal effects on LNHCONS, LNGOVEXP, and LNIMPT in Granger. Though Granger will have causal effect on LNGOVEXP, LNHCONS and LNIMPT will as well. The results showed a causal unidirectional impact of Granger exports on household income, government consumption, and variables on imports in our model. Household consumption and imports, on the other hand, have a unidirectional impact of Granger causality on government spending in the region. That means increasing Nigerian household consumption and import revenue will help increase government spending in the study area.

Table 8. Causality Effects Between Selected Variables

Null Hypothesis:	Obs.	F-Statistic	Prob.
LNHCONS does not Granger Cause LNGDP	36	0.8285	0.3693
LNGDP1 does not Granger Cause LNHCONS		2.7255	0.1082
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNGDP	36	4.1005	0.0510
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNFDI		5.9418	0.0203
LNGOVEXP does not Granger Cause LNGDP	36	2.1369	0.1532
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNGOVEXP		5.0848	0.0309
LNEXPT does not Granger Cause LNGDP	36	2.6183	0.1152
LNGDP does not Granger Cause LNEXPT		4.2234	0.0479
LNIMPT does not Granger Cause LNGDP	36	0.3590	0.5531
LNGDP1 does not Granger Cause LNIMPT		9.3816	0.0043
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNHCONS	36	5.5978	0.0240
LNHCONS does not Granger Cause LNFDI		3.7748	0.0606
LNGOVEXP does not Granger Cause LNHCONS	36	1.1987	0.2815

LNHCONS does not Granger Cause LNGOVEXP		4.4748	0.0420
LNEXPT does not Granger Cause LNHCONS	36	7.2350	0.0111
LNHCONS does not Granger Cause LNEXPT		2.9076	0.0976
LNIMPT does not Granger Cause LNHCONS	36	3.7139	0.0626
LNHCONS does not Granger Cause LNIMPT		3.5060	0.0700
LNGOVEXP does not Granger Cause LNFDI	36	1.5695	0.2191
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNGOVEXP		6.9353	0.0128
LNEXPT does not Granger Cause LNFDI	36	2.2172	0.1460
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNEXPT		5.2986	0.0278
LNIMPT does not Granger Cause LNFDI	36	1.5546	0.2212
LNFDI does not Granger Cause LNIMPT		13.0402	0.0010
LNEXPT does not Granger Cause LNGOVEXP	36	12.1087	0.0014
LNGOVEXP does not Granger Cause LNEXPT		0.1307	0.7200
LNIMPT does not Granger Cause LNGOVEXP	36	10.2091	0.0031
LNGOVEXP does not Granger Cause LNIMPT		0.0642	0.8016
LNIMPT does not Granger Cause LNEXPT	36	0.3566	0.5545
LNEXPT does not Granger Cause LNIMPT		7.6050	0.0094

Note: obs =observation; Prob =probability

Conclusions

The ECT estimated revealed a long-run equilibrium relationship between household final expenditure, FDI, government final expenditure, export and import, and GDP in Nigeria in the study period. The findings of the study supported that, a percentage change in household spending is correlated with a 2.51 percent-decrease of GDP in the short run. While, a percentage change in FDI, government expenditure, and import is associated with 0.23 percent, 0.80 percent, and 3.13 percent-increase of GDP respectively in average *ceteris paribus*. In Nigeria, FDI, GOVEXP, IMPT brought about an improvement in the country's economic growth. The findings provide that 15.59 percent of forecast error variance in GDP will be explained by Nigerian household income in the coming decade. On the other hand, 67.13 percent of forecast error variance in GDP will be caused by the net inflows from FDI for the next decade. This involves that FDI has a strong impact on GDP variation in Nigeria. The results found unidirectional Granger causality effect from FDI to household consumption, government expenditure, imports, and exports. FDI is the key factor to support household consumption, government expenditure, and international trade activities in the Nigerian economy. However, FDI appears to be beneficial to household income, government expenditure, imports, and export activities. Turning to the various roles of household income, FDI, government expenditure, and export and import are crucial player assessments of developing economies' drive-in improving economic growth and GDP. An essential causality relationship exists between GDP and household expenditure, FDI, government expenditure, and trade openness. Substantially, our study offers significant policy implications for the Nigerian economy and retroflex to other developing economies. To ensure sustainable economic development, our study recommends policymakers focus on the inflow of FDI to enhance GDP value in the country. It is strongly suggested for policymakers to ensure political and economic stability to attract more foreign investors. The financial resources from the inflow of FDI can be impartially distributed in the industrial and services sectors,

and thus the nation's export and import will effectively enhance household living conditions and government spending.

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